

Version	Date	Reviewer name/Institutions	Short description of changes
1	14112022		Original version
2	21042023	Liese Gilles	Update on prioritized substance groups Biological matrices
3	20072023	Liese Gilles	Correction Annex 2, number of NUTS 1 areas for Poland

WP4, Task 4.1, Activity 4.1.1, Sub-activity, 4.1.1.2 PARC Aligned Studies

Objectives of the PARC Aligned Studies

- 1. To obtain HBM (Human Biomonitoring) data, which are comparable between EU countries/regions.**
Important for this objective is harmonization of the studies in all study phases + to collect a general population sample that is representative for pre-defined criteria (sex, degree of urbanization, SES) in 3 age groups.
- 2. To calculate European Exposure values on a pooled EU dataset.**
European exposure values are “indicator” values which can be compared with international chemical monitoring programmes such as NHANES (National Health and Nutrition Examination Survey; US, CDC), KoNEHS (Korean National Environmental Health Survey; Korea), CHMS (Canadian Health Measures Survey; Canada) or compared to data from previous EU projects (DEMOCOPHES, HBM4EU). For this purpose, it is important to have a broad common set of markers analysed in all contributing studies to have good EU wide coverage in exposure data.
- 3. To identify exposure determinants on a pooled EU dataset.**
Pooling data from countries together gives a larger dataset and results in more statistical power to enable identification of exposure determinants. Important for this goal is harmonization of auxiliary information collected through questionnaires.
- 4. To study exposure - effect associations.**
The collection of health outcome information (optional) and analysis of selected effect biomarkers (optional) to evaluate a priori defined exposure-effect hypothesis.

Concept

Since the largest financial contribution must come from the countries (55%) and the EU funding is limited (45%), it has been decided to build on existing HBM initiatives in the countries/regions, instead of setting up a European HBM program that is 100% harmonized, such as in the DEMOCOPHES project (which was 100% EU funded). This so-called “multitrack” model builds on existing HBM capacities in the member states and provides the flexibility to contribute with HBM studies that can have different designs to maximize the opportunity for countries to contribute.

Following studies are considered for contribution:

- HBM coupled to health examination surveys (HES), health interview surveys (HIS) or nutritional surveys.
- Targeted cross-sectional HBM studies focused on national/regional priorities.
- Longitudinal cohort studies (HBM cohort or existing cohorts that have been created for other purposes).

! National level HBM surveys are preferred. Regional HBM surveys can only contribute when a national survey is lacking and under specific conditions and criteria described below and its inclusion will be revised on a case-by-case basis.

Sampling framework (= Strategy for sample collection)

Timeframe

A 3-year sampling period (2023-2024-2025-2026) is selected.

1 May 2023 - 30 April 2026 -> synchronized to start sampling 1 year after the start of PARC.

2022	2023	2024	2025	2026	2027	2028	2029

Sampling should be spread **over at least a 1-year** period to have equal representation of all four seasons of the year to enable the identification of exposure variation according to season.

! Preferably within each region (N, E, S, W) all 3 sampling years are covered.

Age groups

The PARC Aligned Studies will focus on 3 age groups:

1. Children 6 - 11¹ years
2. Teenagers 12 - 17 years
3. Adults 18 – 39 years

Rationale for teenagers age group cut-off: In HBM4EU teenagers age group was defined as 12-19 years, but in reality the sample only included 15 individuals aged 18 years old and zero individuals aged 19 years old. In addition, when teenagers are recruited through schools, 18 and 19 years old individuals are already in higher education or started working.

Rationale for adults age group cut-off: Preference for a homogeneous group, alignment with CHMS² age groups and HBM4EU Aligned Studies age group. If the age category is stretched it will dilute the N of individuals per specific age.

! Preferably the entire age range should be covered in each contributing study, with an equal contribution for each age year within the selected age group.

Note: Exposure in children <6y may be covered by a targeted survey focused on exposure through the diet. Exposure in older adults >39 may be addressed in another targeted survey.

¹ 11 years is defined to include children up to 143 months (age expressed in months).

² CHMS: 3-5, 6-11, 12-19, 20-39, 40-59 and 60-79 years, NHANES: 3-5, 6-11, 12-19, 20+, KoNEHS: 3-5, 6-11, 12-18, ≥19.

EU wide geographical coverage and sample size

Maximum scenario: inclusion of all EU PARC countries per age group is not feasible.

Alternative: Inclusion of a minimal number of 11 countries and minimal sample size proportionally distributed over the 4 EU regions (North, East, South, West) based on regional population size.

HBM4EU			PARC		
	EU inhabitants presented by the region compared to whole EU ³ (%).	Minimum N of countries to be included	EU inhabitants presented by the region, compared to whole EU ⁴ (%).	Minimal N of countries to be included (for details see annex point 1)	Target sample size to be included
North	21	2	20	2	600
East	11	1	17	2	600
South	28	2-3	26	3	900
West	40	3-4	37	4	1200
				11 countries	3300 participants

Sampling strategy:

Stage 1:

Selection of Primary sampling unit (PSU; i.e., EU countries) to contribute within an age group.

Convenience sampling -> selection is based on available studies in the Member States.

Stage 2:

Selection of Secondary sampling units (SSU; i.e., sampling locations within a country).

The strategy adopted here can differ country by country.

The idea is to develop a general guidance document to instruct the studies how to ensure their population sample reaches the criteria related to gender, degree of urbanisation and SES.

Sample size per country per age group

The sample size is limited by the available PARC co-funding.

The sample size for which funding can be provided through PARC is between N = 150 – 300*.

For those studies that collect a bigger sample, if the data owner is willing to share the additional data (>300), this can also be integrated into the data pool and included in EU data analysis. As this additional information is very valuable for questions such as identification of exposure sources, exposure-effect associations, and could probably add to the study population's representativeness for the country.

*Sample size that can be co-funded, will be in relation to population size, decisions on case-by case basis.

Geographical spread within country/region

! Preferably studies have a national geographical coverage.

Regional studies can be included ONLY if no alternative national studies are available.

Local studies (very restricted/limited sampling location) are excluded.

See table in Annex 2, where a proposal is made for each country, on the number of NUTS areas covered by a study for it to be considered as having national geographical coverage.

³ To calculate the proportional % per region, only the HBM4EU participating countries were considered as reference for EU.

⁴ To calculate the proportional % per region, EU-27 + UK + NO + IS + CH were used as reference for EU. Calculations are based on EUROSTAT data: population size January 1st, 2021, but for the UK we used population size of January 1st, 2020 as statistics for 2021 were not available.

https://appsso.eurostat.ec.europa.eu/nui/show.do?dataset=demo_pjan&lang=en

Criteria population sample (Population representativeness)

Gender

Each PSU (participating study) should include 50:50 ratio of male:female participants.

! Preferably the 50:50 ratio is achieved for each age.

Degree of Urbanization

Each PSU (participating study) must include participants from all 3 degrees of urbanization:

1. Cities, 2. Town and suburbs, 3. Rural areas, based on the DEGURBA⁵ Classification by EUROSTAT.

! Preferably each PSU (participating study) approaches national (or regional) statistics for DEGURBA. Each of the 3 levels of urbanization should be represented at least 10% (with the exception to go <10% for a specific level if this is in line with the real situation in the country or region the sample is representing).

Educational level attainment - as proxy for socio-economic status (SES)

Study must include participants with:

1. Low education (ISCED (International Standard Classification of Education) 0-2),
2. Medium education (ISCED 3-4),
3. High education (ISCED >=5);

based on the ISCED classification⁶ by United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization (UNESCO). For children and teenagers, the educational level of the parents (household) will be used.

Therefore, studies targeting specific social classes or groups (e.g., recruitment of university students, recruitment of unemployed civilians) will be excluded.

! Preferably each participating study should approach national or regional statistics for ISCED. HBM studies are known to be biased towards overrepresentation of individuals with higher educational attainment. Specific effort should be made to ensure individuals with low educational attainment are included in the study sample.

In summary: this sampling framework results in an ideal scenario in which studies collect a population sample that is **representative for sex, degree of urbanization** (DEGURBA categorization), **SES** (educational level as a proxy, with categorization in low-medium-high according to ISCED) and **age**, with a good geographical spread **for their targeted country (or region)** in 3 age groups.

Samples

Biological matrices

The required biological matrices depend on the chemicals selected for analysis and the age group.

Following matrices are expected* to be collected from the studies.

- Children:
 - Urine, first morning urine is preferred/strongly recommended.
 - Hair
 - Optional: Blood (serum** and whole blood).
- Teenagers:
 - Urine, first morning urine is preferred/strongly recommended.

⁵ <https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/web/degree-of-urbanisation/background>

⁶ <http://uis.unesco.org/en/files/isced-2011-operational-manual-guidelines-classifying-national-education-programmes-and-related>

- Blood (serum** and whole blood (optional)).
- Adults:
 - Urine, first morning urine is preferred/strongly recommended.
 - Blood (serum** and whole blood).

**if the expected matrices cannot be collected by a study this should be evaluated before inclusion of the study under the GS.*

*** PFAS: Discussion weather it should be analyzed in serum or plasma. Note in HBM4EU WP9 advised for serum.*

Fasting state – blood samples:

Fasting state vs. non fasting state for blood samples was discussed. It will not be feasible to align all the participating studies so that all collect the same blood sample type (fasting or non-fasting); however considering that in blood it is mainly the persistent chemicals that are analysed, it might not be problematic. Concentrations of the lipid soluble chemicals can also be adjusted for lipid content of the blood sample. Also HBM studies connected to HES sometimes collect fasting samples. Inclusion of hair samples is still open for discussion with interested partners in connection to mercury analysis.

Sample analysis

Following standard analysis necessary for data interpretation are obligatory in all 3 age groups:

- Analysis of creatinine (crt) and specific gravity (SG) as a measure for urinary dilution⁷.
- Analysis of cotinine to identify smokers/non-smokers.
- Analysis of blood lipids (chol & trigl), only when lipid soluble chemicals are analysed in blood.

! All analysis must be performed in laboratories that meet the requirements defined in the Quality Assurance/Quality Control Programme defined in PARC for HBM.

Prioritized chemical substance groups and selected exposure biomarkers.

In HBM4EU the individual exposure biomarkers covered by all studies is a bit of a “patchwork” (see annex 5). We aim to improve this in the PARC Aligned Studies so that we have **a broader set of exposure biomarkers that has been measured in all studies (within an age group) so that evaluations with respect to personal mixtures become feasible, across all studies.**

Table 1: Overview of prioritized substance groups per age group for P4.1.1.2. a_Y1_GenHBMSurvey

Children	Teenagers	Adults
Bisphenols	Arsenic species	Bisphenols
Mercury in hair	Bisphenols	Metals (multi-elements) in urine
Metals (multi-elements) in urine	Pesticides – Pyrethroids	Metals (multi-elements) in blood
Pesticides – Pyrethroids	Pesticides –Organophosphates (chlorpyrifos)	Pesticides - Glyphosate/AMPA
Pesticides –Neonicotinoids (Acetamiprid)	PFAS	Pesticides – Pyrethroids
Pesticides – Organophosphates (chlorpyrifos)	Phthalates & substitutes DINCH	Pesticides – Neonicotinoids (Acetamiprid)
Phthalates & substitutes DINCH		Pesticides – Organophosphates (chlorpyrifos)
		PFAS
Cotinine	Cotinine	Cotinine
Creatinine	Creatinine	Creatinine
Specific gravity	Specific gravity	Specific gravity

More background info on selection of substance groups can be found [here](#).

⁷ The analysis of SG as a measure of urinary dilution will be added, as creatinine is strongly influenced by other factors such as muscle mass and diet (meat consumption), and may therefore not be the best suited measure for urinary dilution, especially in children and teenagers.

Note: The proposal on individual exposure markers to be measured will be done by task 4.1.2 by M12.

Participating studies are encouraged to engage themselves **to analyze the “complete package”** of prioritized substance groups within an age group. This is necessary to ensure EU wide coverage of data + **utility of the data for personalized mixtures**. **A minimum set of common biomarkers will be obligatory for all studies.**

Exclusion criteria

Exclusion criteria on study level:

- Hotspot studies: studies focused only on hotspot areas are excluded from the PARC Aligned Studies. E.g., study focused on inhabitants of industrial area or areas with known historical pollution.
- Studies targeting specific population subgroups (e.g., recruitment of university students, recruitment of unemployed civilians, pregnant women, recruitment of patient groups).
- Studies with only very local sampling area (this will be evaluated on case-by-case basis).
- Studies that fall outside the stipulated timeframe.
- Studies that cannot provide the basic obligatory Questionnaire information.
- Studies that do not sample the required biological matrices.

Exclusion criteria for individual participants in the PARC Aligned Studies:

Exclusion criteria for recruitment phase:

- Institutionalized civilians (e.g., individuals residing in mental health institution, jail, ...).
- Individuals who did not provide written informed consent.
- Individuals who are not able to provide the requested samples.
- Individuals living in the country for a minimum period of time (1 or 3 years) (to be decided on at national level not EU level criteria).

Exclusion criteria for chemical analysis phase:

- Individuals with incomplete* questionnaire information
**missing of mandatory basic information*
- Individuals who did not provide all required samples
- Individuals who did not provide sufficient sample volume
- Individuals with poor quality samples according to guidelines in SOP's.

Adoption of harmonized materials (see annex 3)

Informed consent

- Must state sharing⁸ of individual level data (pseudonymized) is allowed on EU level. Data must be made accessible following the determinations in the PARC grant agreement and FAIR data principle. See also annex 4.
- Include a statement about storage/biobanking of samples in the informed consent and also state that the samples may be analyzed for other, currently unknown, metabolites. A certain sample volume of urine and blood should be stored for the duration of PARC to allow for additional analysis in a later stage of PARC to be flexible in responding to new research/policy questions or needs.

Note: the points mentioned above should also be thought of in the ethical dossier.

! It is recommended to biobank samples for a longer period of time, also after PARC to have the possibility to use the samples for time trends after PARC. Within PARC no funding/resources for long time storage is foreseen.

⁸ By accepting co-financing from PARC Horizon Europe, the study owner commits themselves to make the data (results) accessible to EU as specified in the grant agreement. Sharing of **individual personal data** must be compliant with GDPR regulation.

Best practise guidelines

Sample collection

- Standard Operating Procedures (SOPs) for sampling, transport and conservation of the different biological matrices should be followed (incl. collection of field blanks).
- Harmonization of sampling material as much as possible (incl. sampling materials, fieldwork blanks).
- **Use of harmonized sampling questionnaires**

Sample transport

- SOPs for sample shipment to be followed.
- MDTA (Material Data Transfer Agreement) to be signed.

Questionnaires

Basic questionnaire + substance specific questionnaire for the selected substance groups should be adopted. In HBM4EU limited harmonized information was available on exposure determinants. In PARC we aim to oblige a minimal set of variables related to the substance groups selected for measurement to improve identification of exposure determinants and sources!

! Preferably the full template questionnaire is adopted by the studies. For studies linked to HES or HIS and that have restrictions on questionnaire length flexibility will be foreseen. From the full questionnaire template a selection of variables will be made that are obligatory and must be included in all studies' questionnaires.

- Mode of questionnaire conduct to be discussed with the participating partners if a fixed mode should be used by all or if different modes can be done (telephone interview, online questionnaire, personal interview,...)

! Ideally all studies adopt the same mode of questionnaire conduct, however, given the concept of building on existing infrastructure we will need some flexibility..

Food consumption

- food frequency questions included in the HBM4EU template Questionnaire should be adopted. So that food categories and consumption frequencies are harmonized.

Health information - (This aspect is linked to project P4.1.3.3.a_Y1_RoadmapLinkingHBMhealth_SpF_VITO and will be further developed later, collection of specific health information is optional, not obligatory for all studies).

Health outcomes proposed to focus on are:

- Blood pressure in all age groups
- Anthropometrics (BMI (Body Mass Index), height, weight, waist circumference) in all age groups
- Diabetes in all age groups
- Asthma and allergy in all age groups
 - *Possible measurement tools to be used: ISAAC*
- Neurodevelopment in children (and teenagers)

- Possible measurement tools to be used: WISC⁹, CBCL¹⁰, SDQ¹¹
- Pubertal development in teenagers (and children)
 - Possible measurement tools to be used: Tanner stages, age of menarche

Suggestion on specific health outcomes should come from project P4.1.3.3.a_Y1_RoadmapLinkingHBMhealth_SpF_VITO, linked to analysis of suggested effect biomarkers.

Budget

The maximum budget per study (i.e., contribution from a country to a specific age group), depends on the sample size of the study (maximum contribution for co-funding in PARC is 300 samples).

Overall budget available for study planning and implementation: 740PM + 1.180.000,00€

Overall budget available for analysis of exposure biomarkers in the GS: 8.000.000,00€

Total	Budget that can be allocated Per study (Total/50) / (total/ N 11650 - 12600)
740 PM	14.80 PM
1.180.000,00 €	23.600,00 €
8.000.000,00 €	686.70€ - 634.92€

**The budget per sample indicated in this document is an indicative budget, the final available budget will depend on the total number of studies included and sample size of the studies.*

45% covered by PARC grant, 55% covered by partner

Possibilities for Add-ons

There will be the possibility to implement specific add-ons to the PARC Aligned Studies. To implement add-ons an additional budget will be allocated to the partners involved.

Overall budget available in T4.1.1 for add-ons: **80PM + 1.050.000,00€**

Proposed add-on topics:

- **Innovative sampling methods**

Possible implementation of 3 innovative sampling methods will be explored:

1. Volumetric absorptive micro-sampling (VAMS) followed by targeted analysis of specific exposure markers.
2. Dried blood spot (DBS) followed by targeted and/or SS, NTS.
3. Silicone wrist bands (SWB) followed by targeted and/or SS, NTS.

If evaluated feasible for implementation these sampling methods are to be performed as a small-scale research component as a proof-of concept. Proposals will be developed by joint 4.3-4.1 working groups in the coming months.

- **Analysis of effect biomarkers**

In task 4.1.3 project "Roadmap to explore the links between prioritized chemical substances exposure and health concerns" in Y1 an inventory of suitable effect biomarkers will be made. Based on this output, research questions to be addressed will be selected and a proposal for

⁹ WISC = Wechsler Intelligence Scale for Children

¹⁰ CBCL = Child Behavior Checklist (https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Jianghong-Liu/publication/258134522_BehavioralEmotional_Problems_of_Preschoolers_CaregiverTeacher_Reports_From_15_Societies/links/0deec53c84168b33fe000000/Behavioral-Emotional-Problems-of-Preschoolers-Caregiver-Teacher-Reports-From-15-Societies.pdf).

¹¹ SDQ = Strengths and Difficulties Questionnaire (<https://www.sdqinfo.org/>).

implementation developed. *Budget available for analysis of effect biomarkers in GS: 1.000.000,00€.*

- **Connecting HBM – environmental monitoring**
Collection of personal environmental samples in a subset of individuals (e.g., indoor air, dust, surfaces, and consumer products). In collaboration with T4.2.
- **Novel analytical techniques (Non target screening (NTS), Suspect screening (SS)).**
NTS or SS performed in a subsample, focus on PFAS. In collaboration with T4.3 (project 4.3_H01).

=>For each add-on topic a working group will be established, that will develop a proposal in the next months.

Other recommendations

Linking to other databases with personal information.

More a suggestion for the studies rather than an obligation, if you intend to couple HBM data with personal (health) data from the participants obtained from other sources/databases you need to inform the participant and obtain approval through the informed consent form.

Annexes

Annex 1 - Details of the calculation of regional population proportions

			GEO/TIME	2020	2021
			European Union - 27 countries		447.007.596
N	EU-27	PARC	Denmark	5.822.763	5.840.045
N	EU-27	PARC	Estonia	1.328.976	1.330.068
N	EU-27	PARC	Ireland	4.964.440	5.006.907
N	EU-27	PARC	Latvia	1.907.675	1.893.223
N	EU-27	PARC	Lithuania	2.794.090	2.795.680
N	EU-27	PARC	Finland	5.525.292	5.533.793
N	EU-27	PARC	Sweden	10.327.589	10.379.295
N		PARC	Iceland	364.134	368.792
N		PARC	Norway	5.367.580	5.391.369
N		PARC	United Kingdom	67.025.542	NA
E	EU-27	PARC	Bulgaria	6.951.482	6.916.548
E	EU-27	PARC	Czechia	10.693.939	10.701.777
E	EU-27	PARC	Hungary	9.769.526	9.730.772
E	EU-27	PARC	Poland	37.958.138	37.840.001
E	EU-27	PARC	Romania	19.328.838	19.186.201
E	EU-27	PARC	Slovakia	5.457.873	5.459.781
S	EU-27	PARC	Greece	10.718.565	10.682.547
S	EU-27	PARC	Spain	47.332.614	47.394.223
S	EU-27	PARC	Croatia	4.058.165	4.036.355
S	EU-27	PARC	Italy	59.641.488	59.257.566
S	EU-27	PARC	Cyprus	888.005	896.005
S	EU-27	PARC	Malta	514.564	516.100
S	EU-27	PARC	Portugal	10.295.909	10.298.252
S	EU-27	PARC	Slovenia	2.095.861	2.108.977
W	EU-27	PARC	Belgium	11.522.440	11.566.041
W	EU-27	PARC	Germany including former GDR	83.166.711	83.155.031
W	EU-27	PARC	France	67.320.216	67.439.599
W	EU-27	PARC	Luxembourg	626.108	634.730
W	EU-27	PARC	Netherlands	17.407.585	17.475.415
W	EU-27	PARC	Austria	8.901.064	8.932.664
W		PARC	Switzerland	8.606.033	8.667.088
		PARC	Israel		
Totaal (EU-27 + UK + NO + CH + IS)					
528.460.387					
North		new calculation	N countries to be included		
	105.564.714	19.98%			2
East					
	89.835.080	17.00%			2
South					
	135.190.025	25.58%			3
West					
	197.870.568	37.44%			4

Annex 2 - NUTS MAPS (NUTS 2021)

The criteria in the table below are used as a guideline to evaluate if a study has national level geographical spread.

	Number of NUTS 1 areas in the country	Number of NUTS 2 areas in the country	Number of NUTS 3 areas in the country	Considered National level study if:		
				If N = 150	If N = 200	If N = 300
Austria	3	9		All 3 NUTS 1 areas are covered	All 3 NUTS 1 areas and 4/9 NUTS 2 areas are covered	All 3 NUTS 1 areas and 6/9 NUTS 2 areas are covered
Belgium	3	11		All 3 NUTS 1 areas are covered	All 3 NUTS 1 areas and 4/6 NUTS 2 areas are covered	All NUTS 1 areas and 6/11 NUTS 2 areas are covered
Croatia	1	4	21	3/4 NUTS 2 areas are covered	All NUTS 2 areas are covered	All NUTS 2 areas and 6/21 NUTS 3 areas are covered
Cyprus	1	1	1	All NUTS 1/2/3 areas are covered	All NUTS 1/2/3 areas are covered	All NUTS 1/2/3 areas are covered
Czech Republic	1	8		3/8 NUTS 2 areas are covered	4/8 NUTS 2 areas are covered	6/8 NUTS 2 areas are covered
Denmark	1	5		3/5 NUTS 2 areas are covered	4/5 NUTS 2 areas are covered	5/5 NUTS 2 areas are covered
Estonia	1	1	5	3/5 NUTS 3 areas are covered	4/5 NUTS 3 areas are covered	All NUTS 3 areas are covered
France	14	27	101	3/14 NUTS 1 areas are covered	4/14 NUTS 1 areas are covered	6/14 NUTS 1 areas are covered
Finland	2	5		All NUTS 1 areas and 3/5 NUTS 2 areas are covered	All NUTS 1 areas and 4/5 NUTS 2 areas are covered	All NUTS 2 areas are covered
Germany	16			3/16 NUTS 1 areas are covered	4/16 NUTS 1 areas are covered	6/16 NUTS 1 areas are covered
Greece	4	13		3/4 NUTS 1 areas are covered	All 4 NUTS 1 areas are covered	All 4 NUTS 1 areas and 6/13 NUTS 2

						areas are covered
Hungary	3	8		All 3 NUTS 1 areas are covered	All 3 NUTS 1 areas and 4/8 NUTS 2 areas are covered	All 3 NUTS 1 areas and 6/8 NUTS 2 areas are covered
Iceland	1	1	2	All NUTS 3 areas are covered		
Israel	NA	NA	NA	NUTS not available		
Italy	5	21		3/5 NUTS 1 areas are covered	4/5 NUTS 1 areas are covered	All NUTS 1 areas and 6/21 NUTS 2 areas are covered
Latvia	1	1	6	3/6 NUTS 3 areas are covered	4/6 NUTS 3 areas covered	All NUTS 3 areas are covered
Lithuania	1	2	10	All NUTS 2 areas and 3/10 NUTS 3 areas are covered	All NUTS 2 areas and 4/10 NUTS 3 areas are covered	All NUTS 2 areas and 6/10 NUTS 3 areas are covered
Luxembourg	1	1	1	All NUTS 1/2/3 areas are covered		
Netherlands	4	12		3/4 NUTS 1 areas are covered	All 4 NUTS 1 areas are covered	All 4 NUTS 1 areas and 6/12 NUTS 3 areas are covered
Norway	1	7		3/7 NUTS 2 areas are covered	4/7 NUTS 2 areas are covered	6/7 NUTS 2 areas are covered
Poland	7	17	73	3/7 NUTS 1 areas are covered	4/7 NUTS 1 areas are covered	6/7 NUTS 1 areas are covered
Portugal	3	7		All NUTS 1 areas are covered	All NUTS 1 areas and 4/7 NUTS 2 areas are covered	All NUTS 1 areas and 6/7 NUTS 2 areas are covered
Slovakia	1	4	8	3/4 NUTS 2 areas are covered	All 4 NUTS 2 areas are covered	All 4 NUTS 2 areas and 6/8 NUTS 3 areas are covered
Slovenia	1	2	12	All NUTS 2 areas are covered	All NUTS 2 areas and 4/12 NUTS 3 areas are covered	All NUTS 2 areas and 6/12 NUTS 3 areas are covered
Spain	7			3/7 NUTS 1 areas are covered	4/7 NUTS 1 areas are covered	6/7 NUTS 1 areas are covered

Sweden	3	8		All 3 NUTS 1 areas are covered	All 3 NUTS 1 areas and 4/8 NUTS 2 areas are covered	All 3 NUTS 1 areas and 6/8 NUTS 2 areas are covered
UK	12			3/12 NUTS 1 areas are covered	4/12 NUTS 1 areas are covered	6/12 NUTS 1 areas are covered
Switzerland	1	7		3/7 NUTS 2 areas are covered	4/7 NUTS 2 areas are covered	6/7 NUTS 2 areas are covered

* For France, the max of NUTS1 to be included is 13 (the 14th NUTS 1 level considers over-seas territories). So maybe only NUTS 1 on European territory should be included.

Maps CREATED WITH WEBVIEWER:

<https://ec.europa.eu/statistical-atlas/viewer/?config=typologies.json&>

NUTS 1 level:

NUTS 1 regions in the Member States of the European Union (EU-) according to NUTS 2021, with corresponding statistical regions in EFTA countries, candidate countries and potential candidates

Administrative boundaries: © EuroGeographics © UN-FAO © Turkstat
Cartography: Eurostat — GISCO, 11/2020

- Member States of the European Union
- EFTA countries
- Candidate countries
- Potential candidates

NUTS 2 level:

NUTS 2 regions in the Member States of the European Union (EU-) according to NUTS 2021, with corresponding statistical regions in EFTA countries, candidate countries and potential candidates

Administrative boundaries: © EuroGeographics © UN-FAO © Turkstat
 Cartography: Eurostat — GISCO, 11/2020

- Member States of the European Union
- EFTA countries
- Candidate countries
- Potential candidates

NUTS3 level:

NUTS 3 regions in the Member States of the European Union (EU-) according to NUTS 2021, with corresponding statistical regions in EFTA countries, candidate countries and potential candidates

Administrative boundaries: © EuroGeographics © UN-FAO © Turkstat
 Cartography: Eurostat — GISCO, 11/2020

- Member States of the European Union
- EFTA countries
- Candidate countries
- Potential candidates

Annex 3 - Available template materials from HBM4EU

Table: Overview of the template questionnaires and supporting materials developed under HBM4EU to support study planning and implementation.

Note: Please note these materials will form the basis, but they will be revised and updated in the first year of PARC for application in the PARC Aligned Studies, e.g. a selection of basic variables obligatory to all studies.

Type of material	Short description	Direct link
article	Tolonen et al. 2022	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What is required to combine human biomonitoring and health surveys? - ScienceDirect
Basic and specific questionnaire	Information on sources of exposure to prioritized substances. Prepared for administration in an interview in pen-and-paper-format	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 1st priority substances • 1st priority substances for children (6-11 years) • 1st priority substances for adolescents (12-15 years) • 1st priority substances for adolescents (16-19 years) • 1st priority substances for adolescents (16-19 years)-legal guardians • 2nd priority substances • 2nd priority substances for children (6-11 years) • 2nd priority substances for adolescents (12-15 years) • 2nd priority substances for adolescents (16-19 years) • 2nd priority substances for adolescents (16-19 years)-legal guardians
Matrix-specific (sampling) questionnaire	Information on the biological samples and sample collection issues. Prepared for administration in an interview in pen-and-paper-format	Link
Non-responder questionnaire	Information on those who disagreed to participate (non-responders). Relevant especially for a population representative study	Link

Satisfaction questionnaire	Information on the satisfaction of the participant with single aspects/instruments of the study. Relevant especially if further studies are likely to be planned	Link
Interviewer's Manual	Background, justification and general instructions to all questions (e.g. food gallery, ISCED-Code for Education). To inform participants (FAQs) and support interviewers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 1st priority substances • 2nd priority substances • Matrix-specific questionnaire
Material and Associated Data Transfer Agreement		HBM4EU:Annex6_HBM4EU_WP7.4_D7.2_Material_and_associated_Data_Transfer_Agreement
SOP for sample shipment		HBM4EU: https://www.hbm4eu.eu/?mdocs-file=2898 Annex1_HBM4EU_WP7.4_D7.2_SOP_Sample_Exchange_V3.0.pdf
SOP for sample collection		The Standard Operating Procedure (SOP) for sampling provides an overview of the general procedure for the collection of human samples in human biomonitoring studies (urine and blood). Collection of hair sample Hair sampling for mercury monitoring in humans – HBM4EU – science and policy for a healthy future

		https://www.hbm4eu.eu/?mdocs-file=5022 HUMAN HAIR SAMPLING INSTRUCTIONS - YouTube
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Annex 4 - Notes concerning data sharing, accessibility

From Grant agreement:**Article 16****16.2 Ownership of results**

The granting authority does not obtain ownership of the results produced under the action. 'Results' means any tangible or intangible effect of the action, such as data, know-how or information, whatever its form or nature, whether or not it can be protected, as well as any rights attached to it, including intellectual property rights.

From Annex 5 specific rules:**Ownership of results**

Results are owned by the beneficiaries that generate them.

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Access rights for the granting authority, EU institutions, bodies, offices or agencies and national authorities to results for policy purposes—Horizon Europe actions

In Horizon Europe actions, the beneficiaries which have received funding under the grant must grant access to their results —on a royalty-free basis —to the granting authority, EU institutions, bodies, offices or agencies for developing, implementing and monitoring EU policies or programmes. Such access rights do not extend to beneficiaries' background. Such access rights are limited to non-commercial and non-competitive use. For actions under the cluster 'Civil Security for Society', such access rights also extend to national authorities of EU Member States for developing, implementing, and monitoring their policies or programmes in this area. In this case, access is subject to a bilateral agreement to define specific conditions ensuring that:-the access rights will be used only for the intended purpose and-appropriate confidentiality obligations are in place. Moreover, the requesting national authority or EU institution, body, office or agency (including the granting authority) must inform all other national authorities of such a request.

Annex 5 - Potential of dataset for mixture evaluation

Parent compound	Exposure Biomarker	NEB II	OCC	POLAES	InAirQ	PCB cohort	CROME	SLO CRP	NAC II	ESTEBAN	GerES V-s	SPECIMEn	3xG
Phthalates & HEXAMOLL DINCH													
BBzP	MBzP	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√
DiBP	MiBP	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√
DnBP	MnBP	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√
DEHP	MEHP	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√
	5OH-MEHP	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√
	5oxo-MEHP	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√
	5cx-MEPP	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√
DEP	MEP	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√
DiNP	OH-MiNP	√	√	√	√		√	√	√	√	√	√	√
	cx-MiNP	√	√	√	√		√	√	√	√	√	√	√
DiDP	OH-MiDP	√	√	√	√		√	√	√	√	√	√	√
	cx-MiDP		√	√	√			√	√	√	√	√	√
DCHP	MCHP	√	√	√	√		√	√	√	√	√	√	√
DnOP	MnOP	√	√	√	√		√	√	√	√	√	√	√
DnPeP	MnPeP	√	√	√	√		√	√	√	√	√	√	√
DINCH	OH-MINCH	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√
	cx-MINCH		√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√